

Silvopasture

- Silvopasture is a type of agroforestry practice that involves the combination of woody perennials either trees or shrubs with feed that is consumed by animals *in situ*.
- Silvopasture is mainly supported by the Pillar I CAP in agricultural lands and by the Pillar II CAP in forestlands
- Silvopasture represents around 10% of the grasslands land use in Europe with a real lack of estimation of the global extent in the forestlands

Defining silvopasture

A type of agroforestry practice that involves the combination of woody perennials either trees or shrubs with feed that is consumed by animals *in situ*. Silvopasture can be implemented in agricultural or forestry lands. In agricultural lands, and therefore in areas where CAP Pillar I direct payments can be fully get by farmers silvopasture is linked to: (i) *Arable crops*: temporary grasslands usually surrounded by hedgerows or spare tree stands to allow grassland sown efficiency (ii) *permanent grasslands* usually linked to shrubs and evenly distributed trees, where the permanent grassland biodiversity overcomes the shade effects and (iii) *permanent crops* where silvopasture is not performed at EU level or promoted by the CAP but has a lot of benefits such as the reduction of the fruit pests because the livestock breaks the pest cycle, reduces production costs as clearance is not needed.

FIGURE 1. Silvopasture share in EU-27 (top) and silvopasture coverage. Santiago-Freijanes J.J.

Silvopasture extent and CAP contribution

Silvopasture represents less than 10% of the permanent grasslands across the EU (Figure 1) Silvopasture agroforestry practices are mostly promoted in the Mediterranean region of Europe as well as in the mountain areas as it is usually linked to the provision of ecosystem services and to overcome the feed deficiencies during the restricted grass growth year seasons (Figure 2).

Silvopasture promotion by the CAP across Europe

- Silvopasture monitoring is needed from agricultural lands to forestlands to make payments associated to agroforestry proved biodiversity, ecosystem services delivery and carbon mitigation promotion as well as forest resilience increase
- Silvopasture should be fully paid by Pillar I linked to temporary (mixed with hedgerows) and permanent grasslands (linked to shrublands used as feed and forage trees)
- Silvopasture should be promoted in Pillar II linked to the establishment and initial maintenance of forest farming and forest grazing (if not included as Established local practices)
- Silvopasture should be promoted in Pillar I and II linked to the forest grazing in existing agroforestry areas such as the dehesa
- Silvopasture promotion should be fostered by cooperation measures recognised at landscape and short value chain level
- Silvopasture promotion should be fostered by the CAP considering the type and quality of products it deliver usually linked to multiple value chains considering the global agri-food system and linked to circular economy
- Silvopasture promotion should be fostered by the CAP linked to excellent well-trained and independent extension service providers
- Silvopasture promotion should be linked to the CAP-Network extension services,

María Rosa Mosquera Losada, Francisco Javier Rodríguez Rigueiro, José Javier Santiago Freijanes, Nuria Ferreiro Domínguez & Ana Couso Viana (2025) Universidade de Santiago de Compostela

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knowledge co-creation linked to the promotion of operational groups

- Silvopasture should be promoted based on the development of the European Agroforestry strategy that should include monitoring, promotion, education, advisory, innovation and research at European and National level.

MAIN CONCLUSION

- Silvopasture integrates woody perennials with livestock should be promoted by the CAP
- The silvopasture promotion by the CAP is linked mostly in the Mediterranean region
- Silvopasture should be fostered by the Pillar I and II of the CAP and the promotion should include both the agroecosystem and the agrifood system perspective

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